

Risks of Rejection to The Individual

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Abstract

(Khaleque & Rohner, 2002) found that those who experienced rejection from their parents as children, adolescents, or adults were more likely to have a variety of psychiatric issues across all three stages of their lives. Disorder of social anxiety has been identified as one of these issues. The individual's ability to have healthy connections with other people is adversely impacted by social anxiety disorder.

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Other results that were studied in terms of their consequences on the person include the fact that the perception of rejection from one's father acts as a mediator in the connection between eating attitude and a sense of belonging. In prior research, it was shown that parental attitudes were a significant component related with eating psychopathology. Other research indicated that perceived father rejection had an influence on eating attitudes. Both of these factors were found to be essential in the study of eating psychopathology.

It has been shown that the warmth, curiosity, and therefore accepting behaviors exhibited by an individual's parents beginning in childhood have a significant impact on how that individual's sense of identity will develop in the years to come. According to Armaan (2019), psychological discomfort, sadness, anxiety, drug use, and future suicidal thoughts and attempts are all factors that might be mitigated by the absence of parental acceptance throughout a child's formative years. In addition, both positive and negative associations were discovered to exist between the sense of major parental rejection, rejection sensitivity, difficulties in emotion regulation, and psychiatric symptoms; it is acknowledged that the findings are mainly comparable to the literature (Ince, 2020). The way in which parents handle money is a very significant factor in the kind of upbringing their children have. It is possible to claim that the rejection of one's family, as well as attitudes held in one's relationships with school and friends, may prepare the way for the development of anxiety and mental diseases.

Keywords: *Risks of Rejection, The Individual Rejection, Psychological Rejection, Sense of Rejection, Individual Results of Rejection*

1. Introduction

According to the findings of several studies, having one's feelings of worthlessness and rejection throughout infancy and childhood has a significant and persistent impact on one's personality as well as the development of one's personality.

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When someone they care about or feel close to rejects them, people of all ages, races, cultures, and genders have a tendency to respond in the same manner. This is true regardless of the variations that exist between these groups.

Children's personalities are profoundly altered when they are rejected by either one or both of their parents. On the other hand, "social exclusion," which encompasses the ideas of being overlooked, disregarded, and rejected, has a variety of behavioral, emotional, cognitive, and physiological repercussions on persons who experience it.

(Khaleque & Rohner, 2002) found that those who experienced rejection from their parents as children, adolescents, or adults were more likely to have a variety of psychiatric issues across all three stages of their lives. Disorder of social anxiety has been identified as one of these issues. The individual's ability to have healthy connections with other people is adversely impacted by social anxiety disorder.

On the other hand, it can be claimed that the internal and interpersonal emotion regulation of the persons associated to the perceived rejection of the parental attitudes is highly related to personality disorders. This is because individuals with personality disorders are more likely to have problems with their relationships with their parents. In addition, the researchers came to the conclusion that a strong mediation impact was provided by rejection sensitivity and the ability to regulate one's internal emotions when considering the relationship between fatherly perceived emotional warmth and personality disorders.

Other results that were studied in terms of their consequences on the person include the fact that the perception of rejection from one's father acts as a mediator in the connection between eating attitude and a sense of belonging. In prior research, it was shown that parental attitudes were a significant component related with eating psychopathology. Other research indicated that perceived father rejection had an influence on eating attitudes. Both of these factors were found to be essential in the study of eating psychopathology.

The greater the likelihood that the kid may be rejected, the closer he will feel drawn to his mother. Children are born with the ability to live without their mothers, and if the mother is emotionally unavailable or pulls away from the kid, whether deliberately or subconsciously,

the child's desire to live is amplified (Ruppert, 2011). Children are born with the ability to live independently of their mothers.

According to Goleman (2006), a youngster who anticipates being rejected by a parent may be particularly vigilant to indicators of this when playing with playmates, which may cause the child to misinterpret criticism that is not intended to be hostile and regard it instead as hostile.

The degree to which parents accept or reject their children's peers has a direct impact on the social development of preschool-aged children.

2. Trauma

Trauma is another word for harm. They suffer trauma as a direct consequence of being exposed to trying circumstances in their lives, which leads to stress. According to Arkonac (1999), p. 436, the development of posttraumatic stress disorder or posttraumatic stress disorder takes place when stress is not eliminated.

Post-traumatic stress disorder may cause physiological symptoms such as weariness, exhaustion, hyperarousal, somatic complaints, hunger and sleep difficulties; psychological and cognitive responses such as time, body, visual and auditory distortions (Akbaba, 2014). Post-traumatic stress disorder can also cause symptoms such as irritability and anger.

According to Akbaba (2014), "child abuse" refers to behaviors such as neglect, physical abuse, emotional abuse, sexual abuse, domestic violence, and intimidation. All of these behaviors may create trauma in children.

One of the contributing variables that might contribute to traumatic experiences is being emotionally abused. The following are examples of many forms of emotional abuse: According to Akbaba (2014), the effects of poverty include rejection, humiliation, disdain, intimidation, and destitution.

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After experiencing a traumatic incident, one might respond in one of two ways. Avoidance is the one that doesn't serve any purpose. According to Akbaba (2014), one of the effects of trauma is a loss of hope and powerlessness.

A single traumatic experience, such as being rejected, may shape us to have intense reactions across several domains, including physical, emotional, and cognitive, perhaps for the rest of our lives.

A conclusion reached as a consequence of the many investigations conducted by James Pennebaker (1990, 1997; Petrie et al., 1998). Pennebaker has shown that it may be detrimental to one's mental and physical health to repress the ideas and emotions that are related with personal tragedies, failures, and sentiments of guilt or shame. This can have a negative impact on both the mind and the body.

(2011), Mr. Ruppert Traumas in the spiritual and emotional realms; a mental injury is described when processes such as perceiving, feeling, thinking, remembering, or dreaming are affected for short periods of time or over the long term and their functions are not operating regularly. Attachment trauma is another term that he uses to describe what happened when the kid was rejected by his mother.

However, for the kid who is rejected, the emotional tension caused by his mother's lack of affection is intolerable, and this causes the youngster to resist this rejection in each and every manner imaginable. According to Ruppert (2011), types of sexual abuse often occur with maternal rejection and emotional neglect of a child, both of which are associated to attachment trauma.

A traumatic incident is any terrible experience that occurs unexpectedly or beyond of our control at any time throughout our life. This occurrence or circumstance takes place when we are unable to make a choice, regardless of what is taking place to us (Solmus, 2015).

People who have poor self-efficacy believe that their shortcomings are the cause of their problems, which causes them to have lower levels of self-confidence and performance, as well as feelings of hopelessness and pessimism (Solmus, 2015).

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In point of fact, the good and bad processes that take place when we are not bonded to our mothers throughout the initial years of our existence effect all aspects of life, across an individual's whole life span. When a person is forming a connection with the outside world, the role that a person performs as a mother plays a significant part in the development of that connection.

It is experienced when the mother is unable to develop even the most fundamental closeness with the child (the child has the impression of being rejected). As a consequence of this, the infant develops fears of being left alone and being rejected, and as a consequence of this attitude, the infant exhibits protest responses. When this mindset, that is, anxiety, is unable to be decreased, distance between the mother and the child starts to develop. This attitude drives him to retreat into his shell, grow lonely, worry about being abandoned and rejected, and move away from social contacts. It also causes him to move away from social relationships. According to Solmus (2015), this life orientation is consistent throughout a person's whole life, beginning when they are infants.

According to research conducted, the emotional harm caused by paternal rejection is larger and more long-lasting than that caused by mother rejection.

Children suffer from trauma when either of their parents rejects them; nevertheless, it is often more difficult for children to confront rejection from their dads since men typically have more authority and status in society.

According to Kohut (1971), if a kid's needs are not met by their parents, the youngster will go through painful disappointments and will have pauses in the progression of their development. If a traumatic letdown is experienced along the line of "idealized parental imago," then in the years that follow, the person will wander between the notion of "defensive grandiose self" and the quest for "the source of strength to be fused" while they are experiencing anxious periods.

People are capable of having reactions to prior traumas that occurred throughout their youth. They might respond based on previous experiences in addition to how they feel about the present circumstance. Some of these events may be painful, and children who have been

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through them may feel tricked or rejected, leading them to the conclusion that the world is not a safe place to live (Savage, 1999).

(Glasberg & Aboud, 1982) found that people who have experienced extreme trauma and whose lives are in danger have little option but to pretend that the events never occurred in order to deal with the emotional responses.

(Downey, Khouri, & Feldman, 1997) found that it is feasible for individuals who are exposed to wrong parental attitudes throughout childhood and whose requests and needs are ignored to transmit the fearful rejection expectancies of interpersonal trauma to their future lives. This is the case for persons who have had their preferences and needs disregarded.

According to research published by Mulkens and Bogels (1999), Kimbrel (2008), and Stemberger, Turner, Beidel, and Calhoun (1995), traumatic events that a person has personally experienced or observed in the past are a significant factor in the development of anxiety. According to Hudson and Rapee (2000) and Gazelle and Ladd (2003), the majority of these experiences consist of being humiliated and mocked by other individuals.

Rejections that have severe emotional repercussions or that are endured for an extended period of time may have substantial psychological implications or even be traumatic. It has been stated that some persons suffer from a persistent dread of being rejected, which is often brought on by "multiple traumatic experiences" of being rejected at an impressionable age. For instance, a child who is made to feel rejected on a regular basis by his parents may struggle in school and in his relationships with his classmates. If the child is unable to rectify the situation, he may continue to experience difficulties in his personal and/or professional relationships as an adult (<https://www.yasantipsychology.com/kisisel-gelisim/reddildilme-why-pains>). (Source: <https://www.yasantipsychology>).

People who have a high rejection sensitivity have been shown to be more likely to suffer from a variety of psychological issues, including social anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorder, and post-traumatic stress disorder (<https://psikohelp.com/reddedilme-duyarliligi>).

As a consequence of this, we may argue that children who are subjected to inappropriate parental attitudes while they are still young are likely to have severe psychological

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repercussions or trauma. In addition, it was said that until this circumstance is resolved, there is a possibility that there would be difficulties in all adult relationships. In other words, the attitudes of one's parents that are modeled for them throughout infancy are carried into adulthood. The circumstance in which children are subjected to emotional abuse or psychological injury as a result of the attitudes and actions they are exposed to is categorized as one of the sorts of abuse that may occur. The majority of the time, adults in the immediate vicinity of children and teenagers are the ones that engage in behaviors that might be interpreted as emotional abuse. According to Tutar and colleagues' research published on the website Kriminoloji.com in 2002, these behaviors all begin with rejection. In addition, Kernberg (1989) puts forward the theory that traumatic events have a role in the formation of borderline personality disorder.

However, studies call attention to the fact that disconnection and rejection, both of which are schema areas of traumatic childhood experiences, are simultaneously prevalent in both the mother and the kid. The majority of people who have a field of Disconnection and Rejection have recollections of painful events from their childhood. It has been stated that the effects of minor traumas are as important as major traumas in terms of mental health, as it is based on major traumas in studies conducted in general. As a result of this study, we can say that the area with the most traumatic experience of Young et al. is Disconnection and Rejection., it has been stated that the effects of minor traumas are as important as major traumas. According to Oruclular (2016), traumatic events in childhood show re-victimizing relationships in adulthood through the mediating function of rejection/abandonment sensitivity.

3. Depression

Back in the fourth century BC, Hippocrates came up with the name melancholia, which literally translates to "black bile," in an attempt to describe sadness. This condition was first referred to as "folie circular" by French psychiatrists in the year 1854 (Karamustafalioglu, 2011).

People's typical response to unfavorable occurrences is one that includes feelings of misery. If this circumstance continues for an extended period of time, the individual may be experiencing

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a symptom connected with a low mood that is beyond their control. According to Karamustafalioglu (2011), depressed mood may develop concurrently with both physical ailments and psychological conditions.

The basic symptoms of depression include a depressed mood, decreased energy, and a lack of interest or pleasure in formerly pleasurable activities. A lack of attention, low self-esteem, feelings of guilt, pessimism, thoughts of self-harm or suicide, disturbance in normal sleep patterns, changes in appetite, and a diminished libido are other prevalent symptoms. According to Karamustafalioglu's (2011) research, the DSM-IV-TR classified the intensity of depression into three categories: mild, moderate, and severe.

Depression is one of the most prevalent forms of mental illness that may be seen in adolescents. Depression may have a substantial impact on an individual's self-perception, interpersonal connections, physical functioning, biological processes, productivity, and overall life satisfaction (Sireli & Soykan, 2015). Depression is the individual's emotions, thoughts, and actions.

According to behaviorists, depression is caused when a person's life is lacking in positive support in some way. On the other hand, humanistic personality theorists believe that respect for oneself is the key to understanding depression. According to him, those who suffer from depression on a regular basis are those who are not aware of the principles that they hold dear. On the other hand, cognitive personality psychologists related whether or not individuals would experience depression to how they evaluated their power to influence events (Burger, 2006).

Studies have shown that the risk of depression is higher in teenagers who have discordant relationships with their parents and who see their parents as lacking in warmth and rejection, as well as in adolescents who have a negative perception of their parents. Family dynamics and the degree to which a family is functioning are also key contributors to the development of depressive symptoms in adolescents. According to the findings of Sireli and Soykan (2015), there is a statistically significant correlation between the severity of depression and both the amount of felt rejection and the decline in family functioning.

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Children who have the impression that they are being rejected are more likely to display irritation, pessimism, and sadness. This implies that they continue their lives as persons who are easily injured and feel sadness within the context of the challenges that they face in social or interpersonal interactions (Sireli and Soykan, 2015).

The fact that the desire to belong is not addressed in studies and studies (Baumeister et al. 2005; Verhagen et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2017) has shown that psychological exclusion becomes permanent, and social exclusion may lead to depression and suicide (Kavakli, 2020). Studies and studies have shown that psychological exclusion becomes permanent, and social exclusion can lead to depression and suicide. According to Peters et al. (2016), one of the distinguishing characteristics of many pathological features and behaviors is an extreme sensitivity to rejection signals. This trait is also associated with borderline personality disorders, avoidant personality disorders, depression, and social anxiety.

"Social depression" is a term that has been used by professionals to describe the state of being unhappy brought on by poor or damaged relationships and the unfulfilled demand for connection. According to Goleman (2007), social exclusion, or the worry of being excluded from social activities, is one of the most prominent causes of anxiety.

Studies of moms with clinical depression and their children demonstrate that depressed mothers usually behave colder than other mothers, divert their eyes from their babies more often than other mothers, feel furious more frequently than other mothers, and are more intrusive when their kids need time to settle down (Goleman, 2007). This conduct, which the kid observes in his mother, may, in a way, lead the youngster to grow sensitive to the feeling of rejection and to behave in a melancholy and angry manner.

It has been hypothesized that a person's response to being rejected is in some way influenced by the way in which they attempt to make sense of the incident. People who believe that they are to blame for the situation are susceptible to unpleasant feelings of rejection; yet, their responses are inwardly focused. Anxiety, withdrawal, and despair were found to be the responses to these observations. On the other hand, research that was carried out on women who are particularly sensitive to rejection discovered that the manner in which a romantic connection comes to an end is significant for the mental condition of the individual after the

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relationship has ended. It has been suggested that depression is associated with situations in which a person's partner is the one who ends a romantic connection. If this is the case, the individual will have an increased sense of rejection as a result of the breakup. (Ayduk and colleagues, 2001).

According to the research that pertains to this topic, it has been discovered that when extraverted persons experience rejection, they act belligerently and adopt the tactic of hurting oneself as a coping mechanism. On the other hand, it is said that introverted people react to the possibility of rejection with worry and isolate themselves from other people in order to protect themselves from any potential dangers that may arise. According to Ayduk et al. (2001), being in this scenario might lead to feelings of isolation, despair, and anxiety in social situations.

persons who spend a lot of time alone are more likely to be introverted, apprehensive, and open to being rejected (Russell et al., 1980). Additionally, lonely persons are more likely to suffer from depression (Joiner, Catanzaro, Rudd, & Rajab, 1999; Koenig, Isaacs, & Schwartz, 1994).

It has been established that the effect of the father may be more crucial in the development of depression (Erozkan, 2004; Rohner & Britner, 2002). The perception of parental rejection in the early period predicts the development of depressive symptoms in adolescence and adulthood. It has been demonstrated that individuals who suffer from rejection anxiety and who have also been rejected in the past have a greater likelihood of developing depressive symptoms in the foreseeable future. This is in comparison to individuals who suffer from rejection anxiety but have not been rejected in the past as well as individuals who do not suffer from rejection anxiety but have been rejected. Negative thoughts might arise as a result of an anxious expectation of being rejected. According to the findings of Normansell and Wisco (2017), there is a correlation between the anxious anticipation of being rejected and depressive symptoms in both a cross-sectional and a longitudinal fashion. The likelihood of recovery from depression may be affected by the existence of rejection sensitivity. Changes in a person's way of understanding himself and his surroundings are one of the hallmarks of depression, and negative intermediate beliefs tend to take precedence over a person's day-to-day activities. According to Weinstein et al. (2016), the addition of rejection sensitivity to the picture in persons who suffer from major depression is likely to provide the predicted consequence of predicting more

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frequent, more severe, and longer-lasting bouts of depression. The existence of rejection sensitivity was related with greater depressive episodes in patients with bipolar mood disorder; however, there was no association established between rejection sensitivity with manic episodes. In patients suffering from bipolar or unipolar depression, a heightened sensitivity to rejection has also been linked to physical discomfort. (Weinstein and colleagues, 2016).

It has been observed that the majority of persons who suffer from depression acquire a very pessimistic schema or worldview as a result of formative events that occurred throughout infancy or adolescence. According to Furnham (2009), this may occur for a variety of reasons, including parental sadness, being chastised or rejected by parents or peers, or the loss of a parent via death or divorce.

Only those teenagers who did not have any supportive connections were discovered to have a link between anxious expectancies of rejection and symptoms of depression in the course of the research that was carried out with young people. According to the findings of McDonald, Bowker, Rubin, Laursen, and Duchene (2010), there is a connection between the anticipation of receiving an angry rejection and the development of depression symptoms in adolescents who do not have supportive connections with either their parents or their friends. In addition to this, sensitivity to rejection has been linked to borderline personality features as well as borderline personality disorder (Ayduk et al., 2008; Berenson et al., 2016; Staebler, Helbing, Rosenbach, & Renneberg, 2011) as well as depression (Ayduk, Downey, & Kim, 2001; Beeson, Brittain). in addition to Vaillancourt, 2020; Harper, Dickson, & Welsh, 2006; Kraines & Wells, 2017; Mellin, 2008; Normansell & Wisco, 2017; Zimmer-Gembeck, Nesdale, Webb, Khatibi, & Downey, 2016). According to research that was conducted by Salahur (2010), the sub-dimensions of adult attachment traits known as anxiety and avoidance have a mediation role in the association between perceived parental acceptance or rejection level and the number of depressive symptoms that an individual experiences. Accordingly, it has been determined in many parts of the world that children or adults who believe they are rejected by their parents are significantly more likely to experience clinical or non-clinical depression or depressive affect-affect than people who believe they are accepted (Rohner & Britner, 2002). This is the case in contrast to people who believe they are accepted by their parents.

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People who have a pattern of being rejected are more likely to have low self-esteem. According to Joiner (1995), adolescents and teenagers who have low levels of self-esteem are more likely to suffer high levels of despair, anxiety, and a feeling of being powerless.

Individuals who were brought up by parents who rejected them throughout their infancy are said to develop a feeling of loneliness and insecurity as adults, as stated by the research of Karen Horney (1945). Individuals as a result will suffer feelings of depression. After then, they continue their lives as persons who suffer depression in every difficulty that they have in the latter stages of life due to the difficulties that they have in their interactions with other people.

According to Persons-Miranda's research from 1992, however, we can state that people who are rejected by love partners and close friends produce more dependent negatively dependent life events and increase despair.

The emotional trauma caused by being rejected almost invariably results in overgeneralization. According to Burns (2016), overgeneralizations are one of the 10 types of cognitive distortions that make up the foundation of depression. In addition, a person who is sad may entertain the concept that others do not like him because of his flaws or because he is abandoned.

There are many different kinds of refusals to accept anything. The phenomenon known as "adolescent rejection" is the one that may be seen most often and most obviously. The second kind of "angry rejection" is one that is characterized by arrogance and self-centeredness. "Manipulative rejection" is the third sort of rejection that may occur. To put it another way, the other person attempts to exert their will on you by using the implicit or explicit threat of deprivation or rejection (Burns, 2016). The emotional harm caused by rejection and disapproval is caused by our own beliefs, and the subsequent feelings of grief and anger after experiencing these actions might put a person at risk of developing depression.

Parents who have suffered emotional trauma often unintentionally transmit their unresolved anxieties and depressions to their offspring. However, in order to alleviate their anxieties, parents become too attached to their own children, but at the same time, they turn their backs on their children because of the insensitivity they feel (Ruppert, 2014). When children are emotionally rejected by their parents, they are more likely to struggle with anxiety and sadness

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for the majority of their lives. However, if a kid feels rejected by their parents, it may lead to feelings of isolation in childhood, which can manifest as anxiety and sadness (Gibson, 2017).

According to Harb et al.'s research (2002, page 963), there are correlations between being sensitive to rejection in interpersonal relationships and having depression. Social anxiety is often accompanied with depression as a general comorbid condition. On the other hand, interpersonal rejection sensitivity manifests itself in connection to social anxiety in addition to sadness. In addition, Rapee (1997) highlights the fact that being rejected by one's parents is related with a wide variety of psychological issues such as anxiety and despair. A study that was done by Ayduk et al. (2000) found that those who anticipate being rejected are more likely to experience despair in their romantic relationships.

Studies have demonstrated that having an anxious anticipation of rejection is related with negative affect such as tension and anger, which may result in hostility, social withdrawal, loneliness, and depression (Ayduk et al., 2001; Romero-Canyas and Downey, 2005). Romero-Canyas and Downey's study also found that having an anxious expectation of rejection is connected with negative affect such as tension and anger. . According to Gao et al. (2017), high rejection sensitivity was substantially and modestly related with depression, other anxiety disorders, loneliness, and body dysmorphic disorder. According to what Ayduk and Gyurak (2008) found, people who have a high rejection sensitivity are more likely to incorrectly perceive and radically alter the acts of others, which might result in feelings of melancholy.

Negative reactions, which are seen as being rejected by other people, being excluded from the group, or being excluded, cause people to experience negative emotions such as uneasiness, tension, disappointment, and anger, and in the long run, it can result in feelings of helplessness, worthlessness, alienation, depression with social isolation, and even suicidal thoughts (Blackhart, Nelson, Knowles, and Baumeister, 2009; Ford and Collins, 2010). In addition, parental rejection and other kinds of interpersonal rejection seem to be the primary predictors of practically all sorts of behavior problems (including sadness, depressed affect, delinquency, alcohol and drug misuse, and so on). (Al-Falaj, 1991; Chen, Rubin, & Li, 1997; Crockenberg & Leerkes, 2003; Ge, Best, Conger, & Simon, 1996; Glavak, Kuterovac & Sakomon, 2003;

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Hill & Bush, 2001; Jakupčević, KK et al. Ajduković, M., 2011; Loeber and Stouthamer-Loeber, 1986; Maughan, Pickles, and Quinton, 1995; Pedersen, 1994; Rothbaum and Weis, 1994; Salama, 1990; Simons, Robertson, and Downs, 1989; Whitbeck, Hoyt, and Ackley, 1997; Cited by Yener, 2005).

Studies that were carried out in Turkey looked at the relationship between a person's perception of acceptance or rejection from their parents and their psychological well-being (Isik, 2010; Saritas, 2007; Near, 2011). Saritas (2007) revealed that psychological distress, depression, eating disorders, anger, and anxiety symptoms were linked with perceived mother acceptance or rejection in a sample of Turkish adolescents (Walsh et al, 2017). According to the findings of the research carried out by Near (2011), the perception of parental rejection was shown to be a predictor of feelings of anxiety, anger, and sadness.

However, Parker (2002) advocated for a shift in the definition of atypical depression as the most prevalent symptom in atypical depression. This is due to the fact that rejection sensitivity as a persistent personality type is shown to be high in atypical depression (Derecho, Wetzler, McGinn, Sanderson, & Asnis, 1996). In light of this, Parker (2002) proposed that the term "atypical depression" be renamed "atypical anxiety disorder.". Individuals who were diagnosed with atypical depression and had a high rejection sensitivity responded differently to antidepressants than those who had a low rejection sensitivity, according to the findings of Joyce and colleagues (2004).

In research that was carried out in 1995 by Lesnik-Oberstein, Koers, and Cohen with moms who neglected their children and behaved aggressively against one another, it was shown that these mothers had low levels of self-confidence, as well as low levels of despair and anxiety, when it came to finding solutions to their marital difficulties.

In a similar vein, according to the findings of a longitudinal research that was carried out in 2009 by Feng et al. with 225 children and their mothers, the acceptance-rejection pattern shown by one's parents was found to be connected with depression in adulthood. According to the research conducted by Khaleque and Rohner (2002), it was shown that there is a negative association between parental rejection and psychological adjustment. Furthermore, it was found that perceived rejection from both parents tends to lead to problems in children such as behavior

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disorders, drug misuse, and depression. These findings may be found in Khaleque and Rohner's research.

In their analysis of research conducted on adults, Rohner and Britner (2002) found that issues such as depression, behavior difficulties, and drug addiction are linked to the acceptance or rejection of children by their parents. This was true independent of the culture.

According to the findings of another research carried out by Anli and Karli (2010), there is a connection between the feeling of being rejected by one's parents and increased levels of both anxiety and sadness. According to the findings of a research that was carried out with college students, the perception of parental rejection was proven to be a predictor of sadness in persons (Kilic, 2012). In other words, it was assumed that the experience of rejection by one's parents throughout infancy had an effect on the structural makeup of people's brains and contributes to the development of depressive symptoms by way of affect, emotion, and self-evaluation.

According to the findings of research conducted by Vulic-Prtoric and Macuka (2006), felt rejection from one's father was shown to be connected with feelings of anxiety, whilst experienced rejection from both parents was discovered to be the strongest predictor of feelings of sadness. On the other hand, Magios, Downey, and Shoda (2000) said that an individual's susceptibility to clinical depression is increased when they have a high rejection sensitivity.

According to Burns (2016), the act of being rejected by another person causes the most emotional anguish, even more so than the harm done to our bodies or the loss of our possessions. One of these processes is known as depression, and it occurs when an individual directs their sentiments of anger onto themselves. One of the most significant characteristics of depression is the presence of pessimism in addition to the sensation of sorrow, which stands in contrast to the sentiments of sadness and pain that are experienced by the typical person. A person who is prone to depression has a persistent belief that he would never be able to free himself of unfavorable thoughts and feelings. For instance, if someone is ignoring you, the first ideas that pop into your head are ones that are rooted in pessimism, such as "that means I will be rejected." These thoughts come to mind automatically. Burns (2016) and Gectan (1994). It was shown in research conducted on depressed individuals by Clark and Teasdale in 1982 that sad memories were simpler to retrieve than happy ones. Rejection sensitivity has been linked to a variety of

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mental health and behavioral issues, including depression and self-mutilation (for example, Goncu and Sumer, 2011; Harper, Dickson, and Welsh, 2006). Rejection sensitivity has also been shown to accurately predict unfavorable outcomes in romantic relationships.

As a consequence of this, it was discovered that it played a mediating function in the association between the perception of maternal rejection and the feeling of despair, as well as in the relationship between the impression of maternal rejection and the feeling of anxiety. It is possible to say that self-mutilation strategy is a method that both men and women who have rejection sensitivity generally use as a method when it comes to their romantic relationships (Harper et al. 2006). There is a significant relationship between rejection sensitivity and depression, and there is also a significant relationship between rejection sensitivity and self-silencing behavior. Those who suffer from anxiety rejection sensitivity tend to blame themselves for being rejected, engage in avoidance behavior, and channel their feelings inside as a result. As a consequence, these individuals are more likely to find themselves in circumstances where they are socially isolated, lonely, and depressed. On the other hand, those who are very sensitive to rejection have a greater risk of developing depression.

In addition, many studies (Gilbert et al. 2006, Harper et al. 2006, Mellin, 2008) have shown that there is a considerable connection between depressive symptoms and an individual's sensitivity to being rejected. According to Brown et al. (2007), other types of abuse are less efficient in causing persistent sadness than the rejection and lack of sympathy shown by a mother toward her child. In other words, evidence-based research on depression has demonstrated that sensitivity to rejection, in addition to experiencing rejection oneself, is connected with depression (Rosenbach, 2013). Depression has been shown to coincide with the attachment type that develops as a result of parental rejection, as has been seen.

Studies on whether or not children are accepted or rejected by their parents have been carried out in a number of different countries throughout the globe. It has been shown that feelings of rejection from one's parents are linked to clinical depression, problematic behaviors, attachment disorders, difficulties in psychological adjustment, psychosomatic responses, as well as alcohol and drug misuse.

4. Pain

According to Bourbeau (2017), pain is the development of emotional agony that has been formed and created in the minds of individuals who feel undesired, excluded, have lost their sense of belonging, and are dissatisfied after being rejected by "others."

One of the pioneers in the field of psychoanalytic psychotherapy, someone's early trauma might be relived via the work that we undertake now. According to E. Young and S. Klosko's 2019 research, Freud referred to it as "again forced."

According to Uncu (2021), the term "loneliness" refers to "the painful state that an individual experiences or feels when he is worried about being misunderstood by others, when he feels rejection anxiety, when he is excluded or thinks he will be excluded, and when he is unable to find a social partner to relieve his loneliness."

The schema has a lot of trouble surviving on its own. We are being put under a significant amount of pressure to keep this continuing. The ability to maintain this constancy is a component of human motivation. This ruse is familiar to us. Even though it hurts, it's so familiar that it seems cozy and comfy. According to E. Young and S. Klosko (2019), one of these strategies involves the rejection of children by their parents. It is made up of your memories, feelings, perceptions, and the physiological sensations you experience (Tuncer, 2019).

The act of surrender involves engaging in all of the damaging patterns that we keep on repeating. These are the ways that we live out our childhoods over and over again. We are still just innocent youngsters that go through the same suffering. Rejection is a part of childhood that follows us into adulthood. As a result, humans often experience anxiety when faced with change. It fills us with hopelessness. According to E. Young and S. Klosko (2019), everything that we are aware of is the pattern from which we are unable to break free.

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In the development and maintenance of psychiatric diseases, experiential avoidance plays a significant role. This behavior may be seen as a reluctance to expose uncomfortable thoughts and emotions (Hayes & Smith, 2021), which explains the phenomenon. According to Chawla and Ostafin (2007), it is regarded as a significant element. According to Hayes et al. (2004), there is a connection between the behavior of avoiding experiences and a variety of psychiatric problems, including trauma, anxiety, fear, and depression. According to Williams (2009), people experience emotional distress when they are rejected, ostracized, or neglected by other people. According to the Social Pain Theory proposed by MacDonald and Leary (2005), human beings experience both physical and social pain via identical physiological pathways. It has been shown that the experience of rejection and physical pain share a same neurocognitive infrastructure (Eisenberger et al. 2006; Fras and Shaver, 2014). In this instance, the dACC area of the brain is engaged (Chester, DeWall, & Pond, 2016) (Eisenberger, Lieberman, & Williams, 2003).

People are equipped with an early warning system that can identify social isolation and the accompanying emotional suffering very rapidly. Being rejected or neglected by other people is, in a way, an experience that is on par with the anguish of dying. To put it another way, being rejected is the equivalent of dying socially in the eyes of persons. Perhaps this is the reason why they have a greater fear of dying. Despite this, research has shown a statistically significant positive correlation between the experience of pain and an individual's susceptibility to rejection (Gurbuz, 2022).

The individual is under the impression that other people would bully them, injure them, humiliate them, lie to them, and mislead them. According to Rafaeli et al. (2018), these individuals feel that the majority of the suffering they have endured is due to the purposeful or careless actions of others. It encompasses feelings such as rage, pain, and terror, and it may be an indication of unexpected mood shifts or that the individual may walk away from their surroundings. According to Young and Klosko (2018), the individual is always on high alert and cannot even put their faith in their family members.

Basic needs of children include touching, trusting, caring for the child's health, feeding and dressing the child, protecting the child from danger, guiding the child, setting an example for

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the child, determining the limits of what the child can and cannot do, being consistent, recognizing the child's feelings, allocating time for him, building a bridge between the child and the outside world, to see, to enter the child's world, and to experience and warn different events and s. Basic needs of children include touching, Emotional neglect may be seen as the failure to satisfy these fundamental requirements. Emotional neglect is defined by Benice (2013) as intimidating, threatening, and shaming the kid, as well as rejecting the child as not satisfying fundamental requirements (OZSERT, F., KAZAK, M., OZDEMIR, EA, & Figen, C. OK, 2022).

According to the findings of certain research (Baumeister, Brewer, Tice, & Twenge, 2007), after experiencing the social pain that results from being excluded and rejected, the emotional system becomes incapacitated for a period of time, which leads to numbness. On the other hand, Eisenberger, Liberman, and Williams (2003) assert that there are neuroanatomical bases that are shared between social pain and physical pain. Accordingly, the findings of DeWall and Baumeister's (2006) study shown that the experience of social exclusion both heightens one's tolerance to physical pain and decreases their sensitivity to it.

In addition, feelings such as social sorrow, grief, and rage brought on by social exclusion might drive people to fear and direct their attention on the process of social exclusion (Solak & Tek Ozel, 2019). Accordingly, the existence of obvious negative feedback is the primary driver of the painful experience of rejection. According to Molden et al. (2009), under this scenario, persons are more likely to lose existing social ties than they are to gain new ones because either their present position in the relationship or their prospects of forming new partnerships become less favorable. In addition, people experience discomfort and anguish if they are made to feel threatened in the context of their interpersonal interactions. On the other hand, Williams and Zadro (2005) contend that being oblivious of one's rejection would lead to the same outcomes as being unaware of the agony that one must experience when their hand touches fire.

In addition, the study participants who were mentally excluded during the virtual ball toss exhibited higher activity in the anterior cingulate cortex of the brain. This is the same region of the brain that shows increased activity when a person is experiencing physical pain. According to this, the neurocognitive function of social pain seems to be comparable to that of physical

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pain. At this point, it is stated that the psychological responses of individuals who endure physical pain are comparable to those of those who are socially rejected. According to Soylu (2010), the agony of being rejected may often result in negative feelings such as rage and grief, both of which might promote violent responses. On the other side, a negative reaction that is perceived to be rejected by others or excluded from the group leads persons who are excluded to experience pain, agitation, stress, and delusions. According to the findings of a body of study (Williams, 2007), it is responsible for the production of unfavorable feelings such as rage and disappointment.

In point of fact, being rejected results in a kind of mental suffering that is analogous to physical pain and instant responses that are accompanied by various unpleasant emotions; these sentiments represent a true condition of being excluded from a group. According to the findings of the research conducted (Soylu, 2010), the second-stage short-term responses that were noticed following the choice remain.

Horney believes that people's first encounter with rejection and other people's disapproval of any conduct, regardless of how inconsequential it may be, is the root cause of their fear about being mistreated by others. He believes that this exposes him to the possibility of being rejected (COLAK, G. V., KOC, AE, and HOCAOGLU, C. 2021).

The agony of being rejected by those to whom you feel a deep connection and closeness is greater than the anguish of being rejected by other people. In addition, the first personal rejection experiences seem to be a component that also influences the success of a person's subsequent social interactions (Ozen & Guneri, 2018). This suggests that the sensation of being rejected is not merely an unpleasant occurrence that occurs during this experience.

According to Yanik (2019), a significant number of individuals who have experienced rejection emotionally shut themselves off, claiming that they "do not need anyone" to shield them from the anguish and wounds caused by rejection.

Rejected;

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- *They have a decreased sensitivity to their own feelings. According to Rohner (1984), those who were rejected by their parents turn to others as a means of shielding themselves from the agonizing sensations that they are experiencing. They don't speak out and they keep their emotions a secret. As a result, they develop into people who are emotionless.*
 - *They often experience uncomfortable negative emotions, such as rage, resentment, hostility, and others, which may constantly be a source of discomfort (Yanik, 2019).*

One is able to determine at a young age whether or not the behaviors of a mother are genuine by seeing how she behaves. According to Genctan (2002), at this point in their development, youngsters begin to carry traumatic experiences into their subconscious.

In a nutshell, a person suffers from psychological suffering as a result of the experience of rejection, which begins in infancy and spreads to other situations throughout life. Everyone makes it a point to do everything they can to avoid going through this suffering (Bowlby, 1980). The refusal to acknowledge one's formative experiences is a component of this distinction in perspective. He holds the belief that a person does not only experience a fleeting sorrow but rather that it permeates all aspects of his life and hinders his capacity for successful social connection (Varli, 2022). People who are harmed by rejection have a tendency to hurt the person who rejected them in return. Emotionally, rejection causes maladaptive schemas, broken boundaries, and maladaptive schemas between childhood and parental rejection, and this impression is painful. One way to look at it is as something that is accompanied with unfavorable feelings. This results in an unpleasant experience and may expose knowledge that is unsettling and challenging to absorb (Varli, 2022).

To put it another way, one might say that the anguish of being ignored or disregarded by other people is comparable to that of dying.

5. Anxiety (anxiety disorder)

Anxiety: The feeling that something is wrong but you aren't sure what it is anxiety disorder fear. These are the kinds of circumstances that might show themselves in a variety of different ways, such as stress and impatience. Anxiety is often brought on by both the external world and the internal expectations that people have. For instance, the belief that a parent does not love them enough or that they will be abandoned or punished for poor conduct (Koc, M., Yavuzer, Y., Demir, Z., and Caliskan, M. 2001).

Anxiety is a significant emotional reaction that leads a person to grimace, haste, move rapidly, react angrily, and play with their fingers. Anxious people also tend to shake their fingers. tingling, numbness, redness, trembling limbs, inability to relax, fear of something extremely severe occurring, dizziness, heart palpitations, feeling unsteady, anxiousness, choking, choking, trouble breathing, fear of death, indigestion or irritability, fainting, body numbness, tingling, redness, shaking limbs, inability to relax, fear of something very serious happening, dread of something very serious happening, feeling unsteady It is likely that the individual is feeling anxiety if they are exhibiting extreme symptoms that are not connected to heat, such as flushing or excessive perspiration. In certain contexts, the term "anxiety" is used interchangeably with "anxiety." Additionally, it is classified as persistent anxiety as well as transitory anxiety. (From the Vulture, 2014).

Freud distinguished three distinct forms of worry: guilt anxiety, anxiety based on neurotic thoughts, and anxiety based on the perception of reality. A sensation of dread or unease brought on by actual threats existing in one's environment is an example of true anxiety. On the other hand, neurotic anxiety refers to the concern that an individual would lose command of their natural tendencies and engage in actions that will lead to negative consequences. The true cause of neurotic worry is the response of the parent to the kid's impulsive conduct, which is the perception of the outside world held by the youngster. According to Gectan (1997), guilt anxiety might be defined as the dread of one's own conscience.

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Anxiety is a powerful motivator, especially when it first starts to set in. A person is able to escape a potentially hazardous situation, control potentially harmful urges, or listen to the voice of their conscience by using this method. According to Gectan (1997), when he is unable to exercise control over his fear, he compares his state of being to that of a helpless infant.

Anxiety or worry felt in one or more social settings in which the individual may be assessed by another person is referred to as social anxiety disorder (SAD). Anxiety, or behaving in a manner that may be adversely judged, or the fear of revealing anxiety, can be described as acting in a way that can be negatively evaluated. The third most prevalent kind of mental illness is known as social anxiety disorder. Patients who suffered from social anxiety disorder were found to have significant difficulties in functioning, an increase in suicidal ideation, financial problems, a decrease in work and school performance, and a deterioration in social relations. In addition, these patients used a large quantity of drugs and visited their doctor more frequently (Kartal, 2022).

symptoms of rejection and obsessive-compulsive disorder, as well as despair and increased interpersonal sensitivity; According to Tuncer (2019), there is a statistically significant and positive link between autonomic dysfunction and symptoms of obsessive-compulsive disorder, as well as sadness, anxiety, phobias, paranoid thoughts, psychosis, and interpersonal sensitivity.

Both moms and dads put parenting approaches that include physical or emotional punishment in the same location on the interpersonal cycle: the often-antagonistic quadrant. It is also associated with this parenting style, which is characterized by the belief that mistakes should be severely punished and punished verbally, emotionally, and behaviorally, as well as intense anxiety and hostility (Soygut et al. 2008), as well as the perception that the need for control is in danger (Komurcu & Pekak Soygut, 2017). Additionally, it is associated with this parenting style. In addition to this, it is connected to antisocial conduct, according to Johnson et al. (2016).

Rejection may be found in civilizations as ancient as they are as contemporary as they are, at any point in one's academic career, in the workplace, in online communities, and in personal relationships. It encompasses all forms of life as well. We notice that children are removed from the game and young adults are removed from groups as a result of tensions that arise in their

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interpersonal connections. The vast majority of individuals report having had at least one instance in which they were unaccepted or rejected throughout the course of their life. According to Williams et al. (2000), being excluded from social activities often results in unpleasant emotional experiences such as anxiety, despair, loneliness, and feelings of isolation.

Because it generates unpleasant emotional experiences such as anxiety, despair, loneliness, helplessness, and isolation, which can be experienced in individuals of all ages and cultures and has a substantial influence on physical health (Williams, 1997), social rejection may also be regarded as a sort of punishment. This is due to the fact that social rejection creates these bad emotional experiences. Rejection sensitivity, on the other hand, is connected to how an individual perceives stress; these are changes that are unique to each person. According to Feinstein and 2020, people who are more sensitive to the feeling of being rejected have a bigger psychological weight as a result of being rejected.

People who suffer from conditions such as depression, social anxiety disorder, or borderline personality disorder are very vulnerable to receiving unfavorable evaluations and being rejected. According to Gao et al. (2017), high sensitivity to rejection was connected substantially and modestly with depression, various anxiety disorders, as well as loneliness and dysmorphic disorder. People who have a high sensitivity to rejection are more likely to misread and distort the acts of others, which may lead to emotions such as anxiety, according to the Emotionally Cognitive Processing Model (COLAK, G. V., KOC, AE, & HOCAOGLU, C. 2021).

People who are very sensitive to the feeling of rejection struggle to form meaningful connections with others and often engage in avoidant actions as a result. They are experiencing a great deal of worry (Celebi, 2016). Because persons with this trait have a tendency to underestimate their need for connection and to repress their unpleasant feelings. Obsessive people, on the other hand, have a propensity to have increased connection demands and a concern with their own unpleasant emotional states. As a direct consequence of this, these individuals are at a higher risk of suffering from anxiety (Ilhan, 2018).

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It is natural for a person to have a higher anticipation of being rejected when their emotional needs are not satisfied by the people for whom they are intended. According to Ilhan (2018), anxiety might be caused by an incorrect impression of rejection. People who have a high sensitivity to rejection and who have been rejected in past social circles tend to respond defensively whenever they face a possible rejection sign. These people have a history of being rejected. According to Bozkus and Araz (2015), those who are more anxious about being rejected are more likely to interpret acts that are neutral or positive as a response to being rejected.

The experiences that people had in their previous life come to the forefront, particularly those ones that were family-oriented. According to Ilhan (2018), the foundations of misplaced expectations, fears, and ideas of persons who are very sensitive to rejection may be traced back to their infancy.

According to the findings of a study that was published in 1994 by Downey and Feldman, people's propensity to overreact is increased when they worry that the people to whom they assign meaning would reject them. These maladaptive attitudes were linked with "simple anxiety" by Horney (1937). According to him, anxiety is a painful sensitivity that might arise, however minimally, in circumstances such as rescheduling an appointment, not obtaining an instant answer, or being held waiting (Horney, 1937). He also believes that this anxiety is a result of being kept waiting.

Studies evaluating the sense of parental acceptance-rejection and psychological health have been carried out in Turkey (Isik, 2010; Saritas, 2007; Near, 2011), and these studies are included in the research that has been compiled. Saritas (2007) revealed that psychological distress, depression, eating disorders, anger, and anxiety symptoms were connected with mother acceptance or rejection of a sample of Turkish teenagers (Walsh et al., 2017). This was discovered among Turkish adolescents. According to the findings of a research carried out by Near (2011), feeling rejected by one's parents is a strong predictor of exhibiting symptoms of anxiety, anger, and sadness. However, in research that was carried out by Ihle et al. (2005), a connection was identified between depressive illnesses, anxiety disorders, eating disorders, and the way in which parents are seen to be parenting their children. Examining the information

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gathered from 707 college students in the research that was carried out in Germany allowed the researchers to calculate the prevalence of the ailment.

According to Ayduk, Downey, and Feldman (2000), individuals who have a high rejection sensitivity are more likely to exhibit violent and hostile behaviors than other people (Ince, 2021). This makes them more susceptible to developing anxiety and depression. To put it another way, persons who go into their social connections with the mindset that they will be rejected are often more combative and antagonistic than others. According to Sertoç (2018), this renders people more predisposed to feelings of worry and despair.

It demonstrates that Turkish parenting is centered on submission and reliance, and that this type of parenting is related with authoritarian views at this point. When assessed for rejection sensitivity in terms of anxiety and anger, democratic parenting attitudes are shown to have a positive connection with rejection sensitivity. The link between democratic attitudes and rejection sensitivity is positive. According to the findings of the study, in general, it can be observed that the socioeconomic position of children has an influence on the anger and anxiety components of rejection sensitivity (Sertoç,2018). These findings were acquired from the findings of the research.

Director and Cakici (2012) investigated the link between the acceptance or rejection of an adolescent by his or her parents and teenage symptoms of sadness, anxiety, aggressiveness, tiredness, and a poor image of oneself. There was a total of 322 females and 170 males in the 10th and 11th grades that took part in the study. The research used the Parental acceptance-rejection scale, the Control Scale from the parent, and the Short Symptom Inventory, all of which were developed by Sahin et al. in 2002. It was found that the individuals generally had a positive impression of their parents' willingness to welcome them. The researchers observed a tenuous link between the experience of parental rejection and symptoms of sadness, somatization, anxiety, violence, and a poor image of oneself. It was discovered that the levels of depressive symptoms, somatization, anxiety, negative self-perception, and aggressive behavior rose in correlation with the mother's score on the cognitive control scale.

The impacts of rejection may linger for a long time and manifest themselves in different ways at different stages of development. According to Rising and Rohner's research from 2020, one

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of the most prevalent symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder is anxiety brought on by a feeling of being rejected.

The psychodynamic school of thought proposes that anxiety may be traced back to a lack of meaningful experiences or a broken relationship with a significant other. Those who suffer from social anxiety, on the other hand, have a persistent fear that they will be humiliated or ignored in social settings. (2011) According to Karamustafalioglu and Yumrukcal.

According to Rohner and Britner (2002), the rejection of parental approval, which is a component of the events that take place throughout childhood, has an effect on the overall development of the person and leads to psychopathology. Another research that focused on the association between general mental health and parental acceptance or rejection found that parental rejection impairs individual psychological adjustment (Bouma, Omer, Verfurst, and Olde Hinkel, 2008). This finding is similar to what was found in the first study.

A person who suffers from disconnected anxiety, which is a subtype of neurotic anxiety, may find themselves in a condition of ongoing tension and discomfort in their daily lives. People who suffer from anxiety disorders tend to feel inadequate, become hypersensitive in their interpersonal connections, and are more likely to develop depression. (1) Because he cannot express his anger due to feelings of guilt and helplessness, and (2) to alleviate the anxiety of being separated from the person he loves, he maintains his relationship with that person symbolically by appropriating this person as himself (Gectan, 1995). This is because (1) he cannot express his anger due to feelings of guilt and helplessness, and (2) to alleviate the anxiety of being separated from the person he loves.

In conclusion, it has been shown that the actions of a person's parents during their childhood may have a significant impact on how that person's sense of identity develops in the years to come. These behaviors include warmth, caring, and ultimately acceptance. According to Armagan (2019), psychological discomfort, sadness, anxiety, drug use, and future suicidal thoughts and attempts are all factors that might be mitigated by the absence of parental acceptance throughout a child's formative years. In addition, there were found to be positive and significant correlations between perceived parental rejection, rejection sensitivity, difficulties in emotion regulation, and psychiatric symptoms, and it is known that the findings

are mainly comparable to what has been discovered in the literature (Ince, 2020). As a consequence of this, the approach taken by parents is of the utmost significance for the experience of infancy. It is possible to claim that the rejection of one's family, as well as attitudes held in one's relationships with school and friends, can prepare the way for the development of anxiety.

6. Stress

According to Cakir, Celik, Cirak, and Kaykac (2008), stress may be defined as the mental, physiological, and spiritual difficulties that put psychological and physical strain on living things, restrict them, and occur in response to events. According to Kocyigit (2019), in the 17th century, people thought about stress in terms such as calamity, sorrow, sadness, anguish, and pain. When the available research on the topic of stress is scrutinized, a variety of perspectives and interpretations of the term are found. Stress, as defined by Lazarus and Folkmann (1984), is an unpleasant feeling that develops in response to external forces that are beyond the individual's ability to control. (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984). (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984).

According to Cohen, Kamarck, and Mermelstein (1994), the term "perceived stress" refers to the way an individual views an experience as stressful. One of the most significant elements that might influence human existence is stress. According to Afat (2018), it is a stimulant, and the cognitive levels it produces and one's capacity to deal with stress may vary greatly from person to person. The amount of stress that a person believes they are under as a result of the things that have happened to them is referred to as their perceived stress. According to Asici and Uygur (2017), a person's degree of perceived stress increases in direct proportion to the pessimism with which they see a certain occurrence.

It has been shown to what degree stress reactions, which may occur for a variety of different causes, can pose a hazard to the organism both immediately and over the course of time. The ways in which we react to stress set the stage for the gradual onset of degenerative conditions over an extended period of time. Time may be shortened depending on the frequency and severity of shocks. These illnesses might be physical ailments such as headaches, high blood

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pressure, and heart disorders, or they can be psychological or mental diseases (Baltas, 1990). Headaches, high blood pressure, and heart problems are examples of physical diseases.

In the notion of stress, feelings are referred to as "environment and person" feelings. It is described as experiences that result from different kinds of underemotional connections that prioritize harmony and their interactions with the environment (in terms of stimuli) and people (in terms of needs, desires, and psychological qualities). According to Baltas (1990), the type and quality of a person's emotional reactions reflect how that individual evaluates the interactions (efforts of adaptation) between people and their environment.

For instance, the atmosphere of the home, how children are raised, the dynamics of the family, the viewpoints of the parents, and the ideas and attitudes of adults about events (Baltas, 1990).

According to research, male and female reactions to stress are noticeably different from one another, and these distinctions seem to grow more evident throughout infancy. It was stated in a London newspaper that was published in 1978 that males respond more favorably than girls when they experience different stressors, and that girls are more prone to display worry and sadness when they encounter stress (Baltas, 1990). This finding was supported by research that indicated that boys react more positively than girls when they encounter various stressors.

Therefore, under some circumstances, not having a need satisfied might also entail experiencing emotions of dissatisfaction and melancholy. The mind is permanently altered as a result of all of these frustrations and concerns. These are what are known as "early experiences," and according to Baltas (1990), they are what shape a person's worldview in the future.

The kid sees the mother as an accepting or interested role model and recreates this role model by copying it in his own ego in order to cultivate independence and self-confidence. This is done by adopting the mother as a role model. The more the mother is able to comprehend the kid's requirements and gratify the adolescent's desires, the greater the likelihood that the developing youngster will be self-indulgent. But internal strife may develop in a kid if the parents choose to deny, postpone, or disregard enjoyment. Nevertheless, the dread of being rejected is one of the negative effects that stress may have on our physical health. In addition,

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feeling rejected by society, family, or friends is another factor that might spark rage (Baltas, 1990).

Statements that are critical, harsh, and too generalized about the individual and his life; this has an effect on people's emotions by keeping them engaged when they are put in stressful circumstances (Guner, 2014).

research that looked at the association between attachment dimension, schema domain, and psychological stress indicated that areas of disconnection and violated boundaries partly mediated the relationship between avoidant attachment and psychological stress (Bosmans, Braet, & Vlierberghe, 2010). These findings were discovered in research that examined the relationship between attachment dimension, schema domain, and psychological stress.

People who have a high rejection sensitivity have been proven to be at risk in the setting of interpersonal and personal stress, as stated in the research conducted by Ayduk et al. (2000) about strategic self-regulation in response to rejection sensitivities.

According to Gadassi et al. 2014, it is linked to maladaptive reactions to stresses in interpersonal interactions, including rejection, among those who have borderline personality disorder or avoidant personality disorder.

(Liu et al. 2014) conducted another study that looked at the impact of stressors on rejection sensitivity. This time, the researchers looked at three different types of stressors: independent stressors, dependent stressors (behavior and emotions), and environmental stressors. It has been observed that dependent stress variables also impact rejection sensitivity and depressive symptoms (Liu et al. 2014). Finally, those who have a high sensitivity to rejection speak more about dependent stressors than independent stressors.

The way an individual processes and adapts to stress is directly related to their level of sensitivity to rejection. According to Feinstein and 2020, people who are more sensitive to the feeling of being rejected have a bigger psychological weight as a result of being rejected. On the other hand, the production of the stress hormone cortisol is caused when an individual experiences social rejection or the perceived danger of rejection. It results in an increase in the production of cytokines that promote inflammation. According to DeWall and Bushman (2011),

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this circumstance may have an impact on progesterone, a hormone that is known to be impacted by shifts in mood, and therefore create stress.

According to Poggi et al. (2019), certain mental diseases, such as social phobia, avoidant personality disorder, and borderline personality disorder, are characterized by rejection sensitivity and severe stress in the face of rejection.

Everyone who is excluded or rejected will have reflex responses, which are involuntary reactions that take place independently of the personal or environmental circumstances involved. That is to say, neither the person nor the environmental factors have a role in determining the kind or intensity of these responses. According to Williams, Forgas, and Hippel (2005), some of the initial responses to being excluded include forms of psychological suffering such as physical pain, physiological agitation, bad emotions, tension, grief, and wrath.

Adulthood is impacted by how a child feels they were accepted or rejected by their parents. According to Kokdemir (2016), certain children and adults are better able to withstand the effects of stress and are less affected by being rejected.

One of the most significant risk factors for experiencing rejection in adulthood is having experienced rejection throughout childhood and adolescence. On the other hand, it's possible that rejection from parents and peers isn't the primary element leading to rejection-prone qualities. Not just the experience of being rejected, but also additional elements (such as genetic predisposition, ongoing stresses, etc.) (Ilhan,2018). In addition, according to the APA (2000), borderline personality disorder is a kind of mental illness that is characterized by instability in interpersonal relationships, self-image, and excessive impulsivity. According to Ilhan (2018), those who have this diagnosis are hypersensitive to the effects of interpersonal tension.

According to Kalek and Lohner (2001), those who have experienced rejection are less emotionally stable and have a lower tolerance for stress.

Research conducted by Rohner, Khaleque, and Cournoyer (2012) found that children who experience parental rejection exhibit less emotional behavior and have a lower tolerance for stress and frustration than children who are accepted. For instance, when they are confronted with relatively little challenges in their day-to-day lives, they experience a loss of pleasure, get

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furious, and worry. They may have feelings of depression and frowning if they respond in a passive-aggressive manner. If they do not take it into account, they are more likely to lose their temper, get irritated, and be unable to deal with stress in a level-headed manner (Rohner, 1999).

According to Maggios, Downey, and Shoda (2000), when persons who are sensitive to rejection go through the experience of being rejected, they go through extreme stress, anxiety, and negative excitement. Furthermore, they are more prone to depression and have lower levels of personal effectiveness and self-esteem.

Sensitivity to rejection, in particular borderline personality traits, borderline personality disorder (Ayduk et al., 2008; Berenson et al., 2016; Staebler, Helbing, Rosenbach & Renneberg, 2011), and depression (Ayduk, Downey & Kim, 2001; Beeson, Brittain & Vaillancourt, 2020); Harper, Dixon, Wales, 2006. The Cranes and the Wells, 2017. Mersin, 2008; Normansell and Wisco, 2017; Wisco and Wisco, 2017. Zimmer, Genbeck, Nesdale, Webb, Clerk, and Downey, 2016). However, rejection sensitivity is linked to social anxiety (McDonald et al., 2010; Bintas-Zorer, 2015), post-traumatic stress disorder (Wang & Chung, 2020), and hostile self-perception (Breines & Ayduk, 2015), according to a number of research (McDonald et al., 2010; Bintas-Zorer, 2015).

individuals with high attachment anxiety live in constant fear of being rejected or abandoned by others and are vulnerable to attachment hyperactivity. The goal of this therapy is to reduce the amount of stress and possible dangers that these individuals experience in their relationships. According to Hudson and Fraley (2017), exerting effort that is wasted might lead to the maintenance of negative sentiments and beliefs. Lyon, Clark, Rock, and Murray in 2020, according to Clark.

In conclusion, if he is rejected as a youngster and if he is unable to deal with the post-traumatic stress that results from this, he will suffer from a lack of self-confidence, which will cause him to experience negative repercussions such as unhappiness, a lack of self-confidence, and a lack of compassion as an adult. It's possible that he'll have a personality that's extremely sensitive to the stimuli of the outer world, shy, and lacking in confidence.

7. The Risks of Rejection

Abuse of children, neglect of children, conditional parental love for children, inconsistent conduct, excessive dominance, and harsh, inflexible, and unyielding attitudes may all be connected with rejection within the framework and run the danger of being rejected. Specifically, danger is increased when parents engage in manipulative activities such as controlling, restricting, intimidating, or manufacturing guilt in their children. In addition, communication problems within the family, reproductive problems between parents, and parental psychopathology can lead to violent behavior and depression by negatively affecting parent-child relationships. This is especially true when it comes to the use of alcohol and drugs by the parent, which is why it is considered a risk factor (Godleski et al., 2019).

There are a number of factors that contribute to the development of an anxious rejection expectation in adolescence, including maternal sadness during infancy, the mother's dominating attitudes, and severe and demanding attitudes during the play period. Inflexible parenting throughout formative years and family tensions during elementary school. There is a correlation between having an overly controlling mother and higher levels of angry expectancies throughout adolescence. To put it another way, there are worries about the control that mothers have over their young children. (Godleski et al., 2019) discovered that parental control in primary school was connected with anger, while anxiety was associated with rejection sensitivity. Both of these associations were shown to be significant. According to Ozen and Guneri (2018), early experiences of bullying, which may be seen as a kind of peer rejection, may predispose children to acquire rejection sensitivity at a later time in life.

When demographic factors were used to conduct an investigation of rejection sensitivity, it was unable to arrive at consistent findings according to gender. 2004 edition of Erozkhan. In contrast to this information regarding women being rejected, Ibrahim et al. (2015) discovered that although women's predisposition scores were higher than men's, there was no significant difference between the genders. This was despite the fact that the predisposition scores were higher for women. According to the findings of another research (Saricam, 2011), males are

more emotionally vulnerable in the face of rejection than women are. It has been shown that having parents with a poor degree of education makes an individual more sensitive to being rejected (Saricam, 2011).

8. Disorders of the Mind

The early identification of parental rejection as a risk factor for the subsequent development of depressive symptoms in adolescence and adulthood is supported by research. (Erozkan, 2004; Rohner & Britner, 2002) Research has shown that dads have a particularly significant role in the onset of depression in their children. It has been established that individuals who dread rejection but have also experienced it and those who fear rejection but have never experienced it are at a greater risk of having depressive symptoms in the future than those who do not fear rejection but have experienced it. individuals who fear rejection but have never experienced it are at an even higher risk. Negative views might be the result of anxious anticipation over the possibility of being rejected. Both cross-sectional and longitudinal studies have revealed that rejection anxiety and depression are related to one another. (2017) According to Normansell and Wisco.

The likelihood of recovery from depression may be affected by the existence of rejection sensitivity. Depression has repercussions not just for the depressed person but also for others around them; it also causes shifts in perception and causes negative intermediate beliefs to predominate in everyday life. According to Weinstein et al. (2016), the presence of a rejection propensity in patients diagnosed with major depression is a result that should be predicted to accurately predict more frequent, more severe, and longer depressed episodes. It has been shown that greater depressive episodes are connected with the existence of rejection sensitivity in patients with bipolar mood disorder. There was no evidence of a connection between the manic phases. In patients suffering from bipolar or unipolar depression, rejection sensitivity is often connected with somatic discomfort. (Weinstein and colleagues, 2016).

According to Weinstein et al. (2016), those who suffer from Internet gaming disorder are thought to have a high sensitivity to rejection. People who have a high sensitivity to rejection

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are more likely to turn to the Internet in order to avoid the possibility of being rejected in real-life relationships.

Early parental rejection is strongly linked to substance abuse and behavioral problems, despite factors like as age, gender, and the presence of conflict in the home. This is the case even after controlling for other factors. According to research conducted by Rohner and Britner in 2002, it has been shown that unfavorable views held by fathers are a more significant factor in the development of these diseases.

Sensitivity to rejection and extreme stress in the face of the prospect of rejection are characteristics of a number of mental illnesses, including avoidant personality disorder, social phobia, and borderline personality disorder, amongst others. According to Poggi et al.'s 2019 research, having a high sensitivity to rejection is a factor that contributes to behavioral disorders, particularly in teenagers who have issues with personality organization. According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5), which contains one of the diagnostic criteria for borderline personality disorder, there is a significant link between abandonment avoidance and sensitivity to rejection (Poggi et al., 2019). Another diagnostic criterion for borderline personality disorder is ambivalence about commitment.

There is a persistent urge to regulate the other person's proximity (intimacy) in those who suffer from borderline personality disorder, which may come as a consequence of a parent's incapacity to satisfy their requirements or internalizing the parent's soothing features. Both of these scenarios can lead to the development of BPD. Abandonment and rejection are worries for these individuals because they rapidly feel social rejection and have the potential to become maladaptive by demonstrating maladaptive actions in response to the perception of risk. According to Kutlu (2018), borderline personality disorder is characterized by a rise in aggressive conduct with the development of impulsivity and an accompanying fear of being rejected. According to Poggi et al.'s 2019 research, one of the potential risk factors for the development of borderline personality disorder is a heightened sensitivity to rejection. It has been noticed that violent and aggressive behavior is typical of the responses that narcissists provide to others when they are trusted with their sexual wants. According to Poggi et al.'s

research from 2019, narcissists do not have a stable, accepting, and well-balanced environment outside of themselves, which is a factor in the etiology of parental rejection.

8. 1 Social Anxiety Disorders (SPD)

When it comes to the facts and ideas linked with the notion of social anxiety, there seems to be some level of ambiguity, according to a survey of relevant publications and research. In many different types of writing, the terms "social phobia" and "social anxiety disorder" are used interchangeably with the term "social anxiety," and the distinction between the two is seldom discussed. Because of this, there is a great deal of uncertainty about the circumstances under which social anxiety is regarded normal and the circumstances under which it is deemed pathological (Kalkan, 2008). According to Bayramukaya, Toros, and Ozge (2005), social anxiety has been investigated under the term of "social anxiety," and the literature has referred to the condition as "social anxiety disorder." Social anxiety disorder is a kind of psychopathology that may develop into "social phobia" if appropriate preventative measures are not done against social anxiety. According to research conducted by Leary and Kowalski (1997), despite the fact that the ideas of social anxiety and social phobia are heavily linked, there is still one key distinction between the two.

Even though social anxiety is a topic that has been acknowledged and stressed throughout history, Marks and Gelder (1966) were the first people to define the description of BPD that we are familiar with today. Marks and Gelder (1966) characterized SPD as an extreme anxiety around the prospect of performing in front of other people. Concerning the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) and BPD. In 1980, the American Psychiatric Association was the organization that first established it as a diagnostic notion. After the third edition of the DSM came out, the most recent version of the diagnostic criteria for SPD were incorporated in the DSM-V guideline that was released in 2013 (Seyitoglu,2018).

The 'cognition' (automatic thinking) that underlies social anxiety disorder and social phobia is the focus of Beck's cognitive model (Turkcapar, 2009). According to Allen and Rapee (2005),

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when children are exposed to external and internal stimuli, they are continually perceiving those stimuli as threats, which affects their cognition and causes them to feel scared and anxious.

An estimated 6.7% to 12% of people suffer from social anxiety disorder (Caballo, Salazar, Irurtia & Hoffmann, 2012; Gonzalez-Diez, Calvete, Riskind & Orue, 2015). This makes social anxiety disorder one of the most prevalent forms of anxiety.

Fear of being poorly appraised by others in social circumstances is at the root of borderline personality disorder (BPD). The individual is concerned that others will see them as feeble, frightening, insane, foolish, uninteresting, or cheesy. Fear of embarrassing or humiliating behaviors such as stuttering and sweating; fear of revealing indications of worry such as flushing, shaking, or heart palpitations; and fear of being judged unfavorably by other people. According to Heimberg (2014), those who suffer from BPD have a significant fear of being humiliated and ashamed, being rejected, and causing damage to other people.

People who suffer from social anxiety tend to be reserved, introverted, and antisocial. They also tend to avoid making regular eye contact and talk little. They don't say much until they're asked questions, and they don't appreciate being the focus of attention for any length of time. They hardly ever talk in public and congratulate one another in a very modest manner. According to Mansell-Clarck (1999), p. 422, fear or avoidance behaviors play a significant role in their everyday lives. According to Nezelek (1999, page 796), one of the impacts that might cause anxiety is the fear of being rejected or of not being accepted, which is one of the primary anxieties that individuals who suffer from social anxiety have.

People who suffer with social anxiety often experience the dread of performing in public, as well as eating, conversing, and attending meetings. These individuals are furthermore concerned that others will grasp their concerns and mock them as a result. They are also very sensitive to criticism and being turned down (Friedland-Keinan, 1999, p. 91).

The majority of people who suffer from social anxiety do so largely as a result of a collection of beliefs that come about as a direct result of the relationship and interaction dynamics that they experience throughout their lives. For instance, "If I say no to someone or get angry, I will

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be rejected" or "If someone does not openly show that they love me, I will be rejected." This is a notion that comes along with being sensitive to being rejected. Accepted – "I was rejected – and I am worthless" (Mellings Adren, 2000, page 246). The symptoms of social anxiety include the fear of being humiliated, of being disliked, undesirable, detested, or rejected by others; these are all examples of negative circumstances. This involves being sensitive to the expectations that others have of you, having the ability to say no, and being critical of yourself (Segrin, 1999, page 15).

According to Liebowitz et al.'s research (2000, page 185), one of the key characteristics of social anxiety disorder is an extreme sensitivity to being rejected in social situations. A persistent fear of being embarrassed in social interactions and performance settings is one of the defining characteristics of social anxiety disorder, which is sometimes referred to as social phobia. Defining the sensitivity to interpersonal rejection Controlling interpersonal connections, fear of rejection, misinterpreting the actions of others, feelings of inadequacy, hazardous behavior, and avoiding interpersonal settings are all components of social anxiety. According to Erozkan (2007), the overlap between social anxiety disorder and rejection sensitivity is made obvious by the parallels between the two conditions.

In addition, persons who suffer from social anxiety have a heightened sensitivity to the negative effects of social rejection, which is comprised of three distinct components. A fear of others and an addiction to substances, together with poor self-esteem and neurotic conduct. It is well recognized that submissive and nervous behaviors, as well as unfavorable appraisals of persons (inferiority complexes), play a very significant part in the nature of social rejection propensity. This is the case in interpersonal circumstances. worrying about how others will affect others at the time, being reluctant to speak what they believe for fear of rejection, unable to grasp the thoughts of other people or believing that other people would fail to understand them (Erozkan, 2007).

Many different hypotheses and models have been proposed to explain social anxiety. (Rheingold, Herbert, & Franklin, 2003) conducted research on the topic of social anxiety and found that cognitive-behavioral techniques play an important part in both the explanation of social anxiety and the treatment of the condition. When a person who suffers from social phobia

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goes into a situation like that (1), they run the danger of acting in a manner that is insufficient and unsatisfactory. (2) Rejection, a loss of worth, and a damaged social reputation are the results of engaging in these actions. They anticipate a catastrophic resolution to the situation. When a xenophobic individual sees a danger of this kind, they experience anxiety, which manifests itself both physically and behaviorally. Because the upsetting bodily symptoms that are occurring and the fear of socially unfavorable judgment are being highlighted, it is possible that important social signs may be disregarded (Tezcan, 2015).

throughout childhood, their parents were seen as being more protective (Bruch & Heimberg, 1994), more rejecting, and less emotionally supportive (Bogels et al., 2001). According to the findings of a research that was conducted by Lieb et al. (2000), the overprotective and rejecting attitudes of parents were connected with increasing levels of social phobia in children.

According to Seyitoglu (2018), borderline personality disorder (BPD) is such a severe condition that it interferes with the functioning of many significant aspects of a person's life. According to research published in 2007 by Erozkhan, there is a considerable connection between social anxiety and the sensitivity to rejection.

However, a unique early maladaptive schema has been found as being connected with social anxiety disorder by a number of different research. According to the findings of these research, schema domains such as discrimination/rejection, restricted autonomy, and xenophobia are linked to social anxiety (Calvete et al. 2013).

An early maladaptive schema is a sign that an individual's needs are not being met. It is made up of childhood memories, feelings, and physiological sensations that arise as a consequence of life experiences such as abuse, as well as a significant failure to satisfy fundamental needs such as constant and secure attachment, abandonment, neglect, or rejection. Emotional and cognitive processes that are self-defeating that begin to emerge in early childhood and continue to be repeated throughout life are called schemas. (Young, Croasco, and Weishaal, 2003; Raffaelli, Bernstein, and Young, 2011).

8. 2 obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD)

One of the most prevalent types of anxiety disorders that leads to a discernible decline in an individual's level of functioning is obsessive-compulsive disorder, sometimes known as OCD. According to cognitive theories of OCD symptoms, an essential role is played by the amplification of involuntarily intrusive thoughts that arise from dysfunctional beliefs, as well as the interpretation and meaning of these thoughts. It is generally accepted (Uncuer, 2014) that the establishment of dysfunctional beliefs is influenced by developmental variables such as patterns of parental attachment and the attitudes of the parents themselves.

They also discovered that persons with OCD have a severe phobia of being rejected and abandoned by significant others in their life. This was another finding of their research. According to Meares (2001), people with OCD who are sensitive to the effects of separation and individuation may be more likely to identify potential threats to their attachment requirements as a cause of their symptoms.

As a clinical illustration of the association between parental attitudes and obsessive-compulsive disorder, researchers studying the scale data revealed inconsistent findings. This was owing to the quantity of participants as well as the scale that was utilized. When compared to the control group, individuals who had been diagnosed with OCD reported that their families were cold, overprotective, and lacked emotional warmth (as quoted in Alonso et al., 2004). Cavedo and Parker (1994) came to this conclusion after conducting research.

According to Rohner and Britner (2002), who focused particularly on the link between parental acceptance-rejection and psychiatric symptoms, the acceptance-rejection of a child's parents throughout their formative years has the potential to influence overall individual development and to encourage psychopathologies. Another research that looked at the connection between mental health and parental acceptance or rejection reached a similar conclusion: "Parental rejection has been shown to affect individual psychological adjustment" (Bouma, Ormel, Verhulst, and Oldehinkel, 2008).

Numerous research has shown that a correlation exists between the attitudes of parents and psychopathology. A person places themselves in a psychopathologically precarious situation

when they spend their formative years in a dysfunctional or disconnected home. On the other hand, it is not entirely obvious whether parent is responsible for the greater portion of the issue (Ince, 2020). According to Alonso et al. 2004, when looking at the common psychopathology, it can be found that being rejected by one's parents is connected with having obsessive compulsive disorder.

Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research on a wide scale that can explain the interplay of factors on numerous levels (Uncuer, 2014).

8. 3 Eating Disorders

Eating behavior is thought of as a complicated phenomenon that results from the control of a person's physical, cognitive, social, and emotional development by both internal and external variables. In addition to this, it plays a part in the establishment of all social ties, including the bond between a mother and her newborn child, which begins at birth. According to Saygili (1999), eating habit is connected to a variety of both pleasurable and unpleasant events.

Eating disorders and maladaptive behaviors, clinical perfectionism, poor self-esteem, eating family attitudes towards their habits, social comparisons, media impact, and so on are all factors that might contribute to an individual developing an eating disorder. You have individual and demographic characteristics, both of which are regarded to be important. Particularly throughout childhood, parent general rejection of their attitude, which is known to be connected with functional and social skills (Kurtulus, 2019).

It is described as the tendencies imposed on a person that generate that person's emotions, ideas, and acts (Smith, 1968; Arkonac, 2008). psychology literature; It is defined as the tendencies placed on the individual. According to this point of view, attitudes are more of an expression of the individual's more general inclinations that provide the foundation for their behaviors than of the individual's more specific actions. Eating attitude may be described as a person's predisposition to form sentiments, attitudes, and actions linked to food and nutrition (Arkonac, 2008). This notion is related to diet, and eating attitude can be characterized as a person's eating habits.

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Eating attitudes may also be conceptualized from the viewpoint that they are established as a result of family and societal influences, as well as early childhood education and development. This covers the preferences that individuals have towards the foods that they consume (Shafran & Robinson, 2004). Eating behaviors that are influenced by a person's choices. What you eat, when you eat, how you eat, how much you eat, and with whom you eat are not confined to biological growth or physiological demands; rather, it is a notion that may alter based on psychological and social factors (Shafran & Robinson, 2004). These variables include: what you eat, when you eat, how you eat, how much you eat, and with whom you eat.

Eating disorders are among of the most dangerous illnesses. Statistics show that throughout the last 30 years, 25% of patients who were diagnosed with anorexia passed away, 25% of patients had a similar course of treatment, 40% recovered, and the remaining patients survived with modest symptoms (Maner 2001).

Many studies have indicated that dysfunctional family connections are an essential factor in the genesis of eating disorders, which is significant when taking into account the connection between perceived parenting and eating disorders. They discovered that early family experiences may carry the risk of having ED, and that a negative family history is a crucial etiology. This information was discovered as a consequence of a research that was conducted by Kinzl et al. (1994). Studies have shown that those who have a family history that is not considered to be credible have a considerably increased risk of developing symptoms of ED compared to individuals who perceive their family history to be reliable. People with ED were more likely to judge at least one parent as incompetent, according to the findings of a review of 17 research done by Viesel and Allan (2014).

In a separate piece of research, Waller and Hartley (1994) showed that mothers and dads did not significantly vary in their reported views about the process of standard-setting. It has come to light that people have a tendency to hold the stereotype that dads are less accepting than moms. Even among those who did not have an eating disorder, researchers discovered a correlation between unfavorable eating patterns and perceptions of moms as being less normative and dads as being more rejecting. On the other hand, when participants in the ED

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group regarded their parents to be unsupportive of them, their eating behaviors became more disordered.

According to the relevant research, it is considered that women who suffer from ED have a greater number of parenting situations connected with high expectations and rejection. According to the findings of Lewis's (1986) research on women with ED, in the Thematic Perception tests conducted to measure the perceived parental attitudes of women's behaviors, women with ED saw their dads as being less loving, hostile, and aggressive than normal samples (Yurtsever, 2014). This finding was stated in Lewis's (1986) study on women with ED.

Canetti, Kanyas, Lerer, Latzer, Bachar, 2008. De Pamfilis, Rabbario, Rossi, Gita, Mazzini, 2003. Kutor, 2009. Vardar, 2015; Calam, Waller, Slade, & Newton, 1990; Canetti, Kanyas, Lerer, Latzer, Bachar, 2008. Research that looked at attachment patterns and discovered that they were extremely essential in the development of eating disorders highlighted the fact that unstable and insufficient interactions between parents and children make it more probable that children would acquire ED in the future owing to a lack of communication between the generations. According to the findings of the research conducted by Alantar and Maner (2008), those who suffer from ED and insecure attachment also have poor levels of self-esteem and think that they are not good enough. It has been discovered that those with a compulsive obsession style exhibit more dysfunctional eating behavior than those with an anxious attachment style (Keskingoz, 2002). Another study found that participants with a negative attachment style exhibited more dysfunctional eating behavior than participants with an anxious and secure attachment style.

In the research carried out by Toker and Hocaoglu (2009), which examined the connection between dietary routines and the composition of families, it was discovered that the participants scored better on the eating attitude test. This was one of the findings of the study. A total of 38.9% of respondents said that their mothers were overprotective, while 50.0% said that their fathers were overprotective. . The individuals in the same research who had a history of trauma in their families had considerably higher mean scores on the eating attitude test than the participants who had not experienced any trauma. In a similar vein, Agirman and Maner (2010) underlined that painful family situations experienced throughout infancy and adolescence

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enhance the likelihood of ED, particularly in bulimic patients. According to the findings of Brady's (2008) research, there is a substantial correlation between experiences of physical violence and ED. According to the findings of the research, individuals of either gender who have experienced domestic abuse, in addition to suffering physical violence, have altered eating patterns.

According to Toker and Hocaoglu (2009), persons who have ED have relatives that judge them harshly and find many aspects of their behavior difficult to comprehend. These families are also considered to have high expectations for their loved ones' achievement. Most persons who suffer from eating disorders are moms. It has been mentioned that they are subject to a significant amount of pressure and are under their control. It has also been stated that this circumstance removes their capacity for self-regulation. (Koroglu and others, 2009).

Turner, Rose, and Cooper (2004) investigated the connection between eating disorder symptoms and the ways in which parents see their children and discovered that mothers tend to worry too much and indulge their children too much. They claimed that the symptoms were protective in the sense that they anticipated ED. In addition, eating disorder schemas play a significant role as mediators, and it is vital to highlight the fact that eating disorder schemas about defectiveness/shame and nesting/dependence explain the connection between these models' attachment to their parents and their eating attitudes. As a person's level of parental anxiety improves, they may start to believe that the people who care about them do not accept or love them because of their imperfections. As a result, people' eating attitudes are influenced by parental indifference and overprotection, both of which contribute to the development of ED. According to Turner, Rose, and Cooper (2004), when a mother is overprotective of her kid, the youngster often develops the false belief that he is unable to handle the challenges and obligations that arise in his day-to-day existence.

In a case study examining the treatment of anorexia nervosa using pharmaceutical therapy and psychodrama approaches, the anorexic patient was shown to have been influenced throughout her life by both her family and her physical state. During the course of her psychodrama research, it was found that she placed a high value on physical attractiveness and that the close

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connection she had with her mother was unable to be maintained in a manner that was both healthy and secure (Ozdel et al., 2003).

McEwen and Flouri (2009), who argued that father control behavior is notably associated to ED, explicitly evaluated the relationship between the style of control utilized by dads and ED symptoms to see whether or not there is a connection between the two. There is no correlation between the presence of paternal behavioral control in the form of monitoring, advice, or punishment and the presence of ED symptoms in adolescents. However, it was shown that fathers' psychological control and overprotective attitudes were closely associated to the symptoms of eating disorders in adolescents. It is possible for a father to exert psychological control over his children by, for example, constantly reminding them of the errors they made as children or isolating himself from them when the children engage in behavior that is detrimental. This may have a bad impact on the children's capacity to manage their emotions and contribute to their overall decline. Because of this, it is possible to think that this father's attitude may drive the person to ED and generate detrimental repercussions in itself, and issues in emotion regulation may create problems for the individual in other areas of psychology (Altinel, 2018).

In light of the information presented here, a summary of the relevant research literature supports the conclusion that difficulties in parenting may be risk factors contributing to the genesis of ED. The acceptance or rejection by one's parents, as well as their attention levels, expectations, and emotional response, seem to be highly crucial factors in the development of an eating disorder.

According to Viesel and Allan (2014), one of the elements considered to originate and/or perpetuate eating disorders is attitudes held by parents toward their children. According to Tetley, Moghadam, Dawson, and Lenordson (2014), poor parenting experiences and unfavorable parental perceptions are regularly targeted for the sake of development. According to Haudek, Rorty, and Henker (1999), one of the risk factors for the development of eating disorders is the amount of parental attention a kid receives in the first few years of life. This includes care, attention, closeness, love, and addressing the needs of the child.

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Sixty-eight percent of the participants in research of 305 girls between the ages of nine and twelve were securely connected, while 32 percent were insecurely attached. Individuals who were insecurely attached had considerably higher scores on physical exertion. It was shown that one's attachment style is connected with one's level of self-confidence. Individuals who are insecurely attached were found to have lower levels of self-confidence. persons who have insecure attachments are more prone to experience rejection from others, to have lower levels of self-esteem, and to have greater levels of weight concern, compared to persons who have safe attachments.

In addition, research has shown a connection between parental rejection and psychopathologies such as clinical depression, drug abuse and addiction, as well as eating disorders. Heller, 1996; Amato, 1994; Dominy, 1997).

On the other side, Saritas (2007) revealed that the impression of a mother's approval or rejection in a sample of Turkish teenagers was connected with psychological stress as well as depression, eating disorders, hostility, and anxiety symptoms (Walsh et al, 2007). et al, 2017).

Ihle and colleagues (2005) undertook research to evaluate the connection between depressive illnesses, anxiety disorders, eating disorders, and the way in which parents are seen by their children. According to the findings of the survey, 6.9% of people suffer from eating disorders. It has been reported that this percentage is much greater for students who identify as female. It was revealed that maternal control and overprotective attitudes were connected with dietary psychopathology (Kurtulus, 2019). This was discovered when researchers investigated the connection between eating disorders and the rejection of children by their parents.

Jones (2006) undertook an investigation on the link between father-daughter relationships and dietary psychopathology, and the findings were presented in research. He contrasted 66 women who had been diagnosed with an eating problem to 50 healthy controls as part of his investigation into the link between people's parental attitudes, basic beliefs, and the psychopathology of eating. fundamental beliefs such as abandonment, shame, and hypersensitivity to damage have been demonstrated to have a mediating role in this predictive association (Kurtulus, 2019). Rejection and excessive protection of fathers both predict the

psychopathology of eating, and fundamental beliefs such as these also play a role in the predictive relationship.

Psychopathologies such as parental rejection, obsessive-compulsive disorder (Alonso et al. 2004), anxiety disorders (Cunha & Santo, 2013; Giaouzi & Giovazolias, 2015), eating disorders (Herraiz-Serran et al. 2015), depression, and suicide are examples of frequent psychopathologies. It was discovered that crime and behavior issues (Simons, Robertson & Downes, 1988. Kim et al., 2003) and drug usage (Azevedo, Simes, Marques, Cunha & Santo, 2013) are associated (Ince, 2020).

According to Harris (2021), avoidance of experience is at the root of a wide range of mental health issues, including anxiety, sadness, addiction to substances, alcoholism, and eating disorders. The idea of avoiding unpleasant experiences is one that is often discussed, particularly in more recent studies. When the literature is searched (Cowdrey and Park, 2012), sleep quality (Waldeck et al., 2020), impaired eating behavior (Fahrenkamp et al., 2019), cancer-related pain and stress (Brown et al., 2020), interpersonal problems (Gerhart et al., 2014), experiential avoidance, attachment (Shear, 2010), fear of death (Belsivo, 2010), suicidal ideation (Roush et al., 2017), and exclusion (Tyndall et al., 2018) (Gurbuz, 2022)).

When the literature is examined, it has been determined that early maladaptive schemas are associated with various psychiatric disorders such as depression, personality disorders and eating disorders (eg, Hinrichsen, Waller & Emanuelli, 2004: 784-787; Joyev & Jackson, 2004: 467-478; Reeves & Taylor, 2007: 96-104; Riso et al., 2006: 515-529). There have only been a few of research that have investigated the link between early maladaptive schemas and social anxiety. Studies have shown that early maladaptive schemas in areas such as separation and exclusion/rejection, autonomy and achievement limitations, and orientation to others play a role in the development and maintenance of social anxiety (Calvete, 2014: 735-746; Calvete, Orue, & Hankin, 2013a: 278-288; Calvete, Orue, & Hankin, 2015: 85-99; Mairret, Boag, & Warburton, 2014: 171-190; Pinto-Gouveia, Castilho, Gallardo, & Cunha, 2006: 571-584), (Zorer, 2015).

The first maladaptive schemas that are going to be covered in this research are one factor that is hypothesized to be created and/or perpetuated by deficiencies in eating attitude. Young (1999) contends that early maladaptive schemas are the source of psychological issues and are

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responsible for their development. An obviously disordered schema is one risk factor for the development of eating disorders, and it may arise through interactions with parents during the earliest years of a child's existence (Young, 1999; Batur, 2004; Cooper, Todd, & Wells, 1998; Jones, Leung, & Harris, 2007; Leung, Waller, & Thomas, 1999; Leung, Waller, & Thomas, 1999); Sines, Waller, Meyer, and Wigley (2008)).

However, while looking at the features of individuals who suffered from bulimia neurosis, it was discovered that their families lacked support and understanding. According to Baydemir (1999), it has been hypothesized that children who grow up in such households may acquire a tendency to throw up as an expression of animosity and rejection towards members of their own family. According to Alden and Taylor (2004), persons who suffer from social appearance anxiety often and thoroughly consider the chance that they would be rejected by other people. The presence of this possibility makes it harder for these individuals to exhibit sincerity and warmth in their interpersonal connections.

Disorders of feeding and eating are caused by a breakdown in crucial attachment interactions in early infancy. One of these conditions is called rumination disorder, and it's been linked to an increased risk of infant rejection and the anticipation of being rejected. The swallowing and re-chewing of partly digested food without substantial feelings of nausea, desires, or indigestion is the defining characteristic of rumination disorder. After three months, it often begins to manifest itself. Children who have intellectual challenges often engage in this activity as a kind of self-stimulating behavior. By maintaining the act of feeding, the kid communicates their expectation that the mother will provide them with sufficient and consistent care as well as enjoyment. According to Solmus (2010), ruminative disorders lead mothers to be reluctant to eat and engage in avoidance behaviors. This, in turn, raises the baby's level of rejection and the baby's anticipation of being rejected.

Relationships within the family are one of the most prominent factors that might bring to eating disorders. The majority of people who have been diagnosed with BN have poor family ties, according to a review of their family histories. Patients often report that their parents are cold and uncaring toward them.

On the other hand, it has been shown that the presence of excessive emotions of loneliness and rejection have a role in the development of psychopathological eating attitudes. Studies have indicated a link between eating psychopathology and loneliness, which is very similar to the association between abandonment schema and loneliness and perceived father rejection. However, the results of this research showed that perceived father rejection did not play a mediation function in this relationship. Instead, it was discovered that there was a stronger association between people's experiences of rejection and their dads' perceptions of rejection, and that the perceived father's sense of rejection served as the mediator in the interaction between the rejection sub-dimension (Kurtulus, 2019).

According to Toker and Hocaoglu (2009), the most essential factors that determine how well a family functions are its communication patterns inside the family, its structure, its ties with one another, and the ways in which its members interact with one another. It is hypothesized that feeling rejected by one's parents may have a role in developing unhealthy eating patterns (Cevizci, 2021).

8. 4 Conduct Disorders

Children who have been diagnosed with conduct disorder engage in behaviors such as outbursts of anger, lying, stealing, committing acts of physical aggressiveness against other people and animals, starting fires, causing damage to property, and engaging in sexual activity against their will. According to Solmus (2010), it is more prevalent in males and teenagers, affecting 6% to 16% of boys but just 2% to 9% of girls.

From the perspective of the attachment process, behavioral abnormalities in relationships, excessive parental control and rigorous discipline, excessive indifference, neglect, insufficient or inconsistent care for children, physical or sexual abuse, growing up in a crowded family setting, and orphanages are all factors that might negatively affect a child's development. One may say that these factors are what first led to the development of the condition. According to Solmus (2010), one of the most crucial diagnostic criteria for reactive attachment disorder is

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the presence of aggressive behavior against animals. This aggressive conduct is a symptom of the disease.

According to the research conducted by Khaleque and Rohner (2002), there is a negative association between parental rejection and psychological adjustment. Additionally, it has been shown that the child's perception of being rejected by their parents may lead to conditions like as behavioral disorders, drug use, and depression (Ince,2020).

According to Rohner and Britner (2002), depression, behavioral disorders, and drug use in adult studies are problems associated to parental acceptance-rejection (Ince,2020). These issues are not influenced by culture and are independent of it.

Many studies suggest that insecure attachment styles are predictors of anxiety, depressive, and behavioral problems in adults, while secure attachment styles are related with healthy processes (Kesebir, Kavzoglu, & Ustundag, 2011). This is based on an examination of the whole body of research that has been conducted. On the other side, persons who have an insecure attachment style have negative expectations about their interactions with other people, they avoid becoming involved in relationships out of fear of being hurt or rejected, and it has been underlined that they are unable to manage their emotions sufficiently (Waters & Cummings, 2000). In addition, persons who have an insecure attachment style are more likely to adopt coping mechanisms (such as repressing their feelings) when they feel threatened or under stress. This results in an increase in worry and stress, as well as a propensity to fear abandonment and rejection as a result of the poor traits that they themselves possess (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2007).

Conclusion

It is possible to say that the internal and interpersonal emotion management of persons associated to the perceived rejection of the parental attitudes is highly related to personality

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disorders. This is something that can be mentioned because of the relationship between the two. In addition, the researchers came to the conclusion that a strong mediation impact was provided by rejection sensitivity and the ability to regulate one's internal emotions when considering the relationship between fatherly perceived emotional warmth and personality disorders.

The degree to which parents accept or reject their children's peers has a direct impact on the social development of preschool-aged children.

On the other hand, conditions such as rejection, disapproval, feelings of unworthiness, failure, loneliness, dependence, and anger, as well as other related emotional swings and mental illnesses, might induce (Lime, 2023).

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